

2-Hydroxy-4-Methylacetophenone Oxime (HMAOX) as an Analytical Reagent : Studies on Palladium Chelate

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2-Hydroxy-4-methylacetophenone oxime (HMAOX) has been used as a reagent for gravimetric determination of palladium and for its separation from several cations and anions. Palladium is quantitatively precipitated by HMAOX between pH range 1.5-4.0. After drying the precipitate at 120°, its composition corresponds to the formula $\text{Pd}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2$. Interference due to copper(II) and titanium(IV) has been eliminated by masking with EDTA and NaF or KF respectively and in other cases by suitable control of pH.

DIFFERENT methods used for the gravimetric determination of palladium have been reviewed critically by Beamish¹. Many orthophenolic oximes²⁻⁶ have already been reported as analytical reagents for palladium. 2-Hydroxy-4-methylacetophenone oxime (HMAOX)⁷ has now been successfully employed for the gravimetric determination of palladium, its separation from a number of ions and determination of palladium and nickel in their binary mixture.

The present work on the reaction of HMAOX with Pd(II) was undertaken with the intention to introduce a new ligand for the gravimetric determination of palladium. HMAOX gives yellow precipitate with palladium between pH range of 1.0 to 4.0.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. Grade. Stock solution of palladium(II) was prepared by dissolving palladium chloride in A.R. HCl, diluting the solution and determining its Pd(II) content with dimethylglyoxime⁸. Solutions of other ions were prepared from samples of corresponding salts. An ethanolic solution of the reagent was employed and pH was adjusted using hydrochloric acid and sodium acetate.

Synthesis of the reagent :

2-Hydroxy-4-methylacetophenone⁷ was obtained in almost quantitative yield by Fries migration of *m*-cresylacetate⁹ in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. Its oxime⁷ was prepared by the reaction of above ketone with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and potassium hydroxide (40%) in dilute ethanol. It was crystallised from petroleum, m.p. 102°.

Determination of palladium :

A known volume of palladium solution taken in a beaker was diluted to about 150 ml and the pH was

adjusted to 2.0. The solution was warmed to 60-70° and a calculated volume of ethanolic solution of the reagent (1%) was added with constant stirring until no more precipitation took place on adding excess of the reagent solution. The precipitate was digested on water-bath for 30 min. It was then filtered hot through a sintered glass crucible (G_4), washed with hot water (60-70°) to remove foreign ions and the buffer adhering the precipitate. The precipitate was finally washed several time with 60 per cent ethanol to remove excess of the reagent. The precipitate was dried at 120° to constant weight. The metal content was determined using factor 0.2449. The results of some of the estimations are given in Table 1.

TABLE-1 DETERMINATION OF PALLADIUM(II)

Pd taken, (mg)	Wt. of complex, (mg)	Pd found, (mg)	Error (mg)
2.608	10.6	2.596	-0.012
9.780	39.9	9.772	-0.008
32.600	133.2	32.630	-0.030

Effect of pH :

Palladium was precipitated at different pH values adjusted with HCl and sodium acetate solutions maintaining all other conditions identical. The precipitation commenced at pH 1.0 and was quantitative between pH 1.5 and 4.0.

Determination of palladium in presence of foreign ions :

To study the effect of foreign ions on gravimetric determination of palladium, 20-25 mg of various cations as well as anions were added to a known volume of Pd(II) solution (6.52 mg Pd) at pH 2.0 and estimations were carried out as mentioned above. Hg(II), Pb(II), As(III), Cd(II), Al(III), Mn(II), Zn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Ba(II), Sr(II), Ca(II)

and Mg(II) were found not to form any insoluble complex with the reagent at pH below 3.5, hence they created no interference in the estimation of Pd(II) by the reagent at pH 2.0. Fe(III) ion which formed soluble complex with the reagent at lower pH was completely masked by adding tartaric acid (2.0 g) before adding the reagent. Cu(II), Ti(IV), vanadate and molybdate ions formed insoluble complexes¹⁰ with the reagent at low pH and these ions interfere in the gravimetric determination of Pd(II). Interference due to Cu(II) was removed by masking with EDTA (0.5 g) before adding the reagent. Interference due to Ti(IV), vanadate and molybdate was removed by adding NaF or KF (0.5 g) as masking agent before adding the reagent. It was found that anions like tartarate, citrate, nitrate, fluoride do not interfere in the estimation of Pd(II).

Separation and determination of palladium and nickel :

Definite volume of standard solutions of palladium and nickel ions were mixed together and diluted to 200 ml. pH of solution was adjusted to 2.0. The yellow coloured palladium chelate precipitated was estimated gravimetrically as above. The filtrate and washings after the removal of palladium chelate were collected for the estimation of nickel. Its pH was adjusted to 5.5 using sodium acetate solution and nickel was estimated gravimetrically¹¹. Some of the results given in Table 2 show that palladium and nickel can be accurately determined when present in the same solution.

TABLE—2 ESTIMATION OF PALLADIUM(II) AND NICKEL(II)

Metal taken (mg)		Wt. of Complex, (mg)		Metal found, (mg)		Error, (mg)	
Pd(II)	Ni(II)	Pd(II)	Ni(II)	Pd(II)	Ni(II)	Pd(II)	Ni(II)
2.608	3.0	10.6	19.7	2.596	2.990	+0.012	-0.01
13.04	18.0	53.0	118.5	12.98	17.99	-0.06	-0.01
26.08	30.0	106.7	197.0	26.13	29.90	+0.05	-0.10

Metal-ligand composition :

Direct conductometric titrations have been done to ascertain the palladium HMAOX ratio in palladium complex. Different volumes of the prepared $\frac{M}{50}$ Pd(II) solution were taken in beakers and in each beaker varying volumes of the prepared $\frac{M}{50}$ reagent solution and absolute alcohol were added in such a way that the total volume in each beaker remained 40 ml. The conductance of the solutions in each beaker were then determined. Graphs between the conductance against the volume of the reagent added for a fixed amount of palladium indicated 1 : 2 metal-ligand ratio for palladium complex.

The palladium chelate was analysed for its carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen content to determine the composition. The metal content was determined by standard analytical method (Found : C, 49.4 ; H, 4.4 ; N, 6.7 ; Pd, 24.32 ; Calc. C, 49.7 ; H, 4.6 ; N, 6.4 ; Pd, 24.49). The composition of chelate corresponds to the formula $\text{Pd}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2$ in which metal-ligand ratio is 1 : 2. The molecular weight determined cryoscopically using camphor as solvent showed the chelate to be monomeric, i.e., the chelate could be represented by ML_2 . The 1 : 2 stoichiometry is confirmed by Job's method of continuous variation. The palladium complex was experimentally found to be diamagnetic, as expected.

On the basis of above results following structure is suggested to the metal chelate.

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References

1. F. E. BEAMISH; *Talanta*, 1958, **1**, 3 ; 1965, **12**, 743 ; 1966, **13**, 773.
2. S. N. PODDAR, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1963, **28**, 586.
3. H. HOLZER, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1933, **93**, 392.
4. V. M. PESHKOVA, V. I. SHIENSKAYA and A. I. ROSEVSKAYA, *Vestn.*, Mosk. Univ., 9, No. 5, *Ser. Mat. i. Estersven Nauk* 1954, **3**, 88.
5. D. P. GOEL, K. C. TRIKHA and R. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1969, **32**, 62.
6. D. N. PATKAR, N. D. TAMBAT, R. N. MERCHANT, *Curr. Sci.*, 1973, **42**, 818.
7. J. F. EIJKMAN, *J. Chem. Soc. Abs.*, 1904, **85**, 664.
8. A. CLAUS and J. HIRSCH, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1889, **39**, 62.
9. A. I. VOGEL: A Test Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis, Longman Green and Co. Ltd., London, 1962, p. 511.
10. L. C. JHAVERI, G. S. PATEL and V. M. THAKOR, *J. Gujarat Univ.*, 1973, **17**, 43 ; 1975, **18**, 70.
11. L. C. JHAVERI, G. S. PATEL and V. M. THAKOR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 730.